

Finding God in the Human Heart and History Theological Vision of Pope Francis in *Totum Amoris Est*

Thomas Karimundackal, SJ

Abstract

The paper provides a comprehensive overview of Pope Francis' Apostolic Letter *Totum Amoris Est* (*Everything Pertains to Love*), especially his theological visions for the church and society in the Letter. It provides a deeper understanding of Pope Francis' visions and concerns for a rapidly changing world. While reflecting upon the spiritual legacy of St. Francis de Sales, Pope Francis relates the Saint's life and mission to the church and society, such as the need for proclaiming the Gospel in changing times, testing love through God's grace and discernment, experiencing devotion as love, finding God in the human heart and history, a renewed church and society, a theology immersed in prayer and community, a new style of dialogue, discovering the beauty and joy of loving, etc.

Introduction

On the 400th death anniversary of St. Francis de Sales, Pope Francis issues an Apostolic Letter entitled *Totum Amoris Est* (*Everything Pertains to Love*) in which the Pope summarizes the spiritual legacy of St. Francis de Sales. The title, *Totum Amoris Est*, comes from the preface of the Saint's book *Treatise on the Love of God*, where he affirms that "In Holy Church, everything pertains to love, lives in love, is done for love and comes from love." Describing him as a fine "interpreter" of his time (*Amoris*, p. 23-24),¹ an "extraordinary director of souls" (*Amoris*, p. 18), the "Doctor of the divine love" (*Amoris*, p. 11), Pope Francis highlights the Saint's ability to help people to seek God in love, charity, joy, and freedom in an era of great changes. Pope Francis argues that the great vocation of this great saint, the

¹ All the references from the Apostolic Letter *Totum Amoris Est* are from Pope Francis, Apostolic Letter *Totum Amoris Est* (*Everything Pertains to Love*): On the Fourth Centenary of the Death of Saint Francis de Sales (Mumbai: St. Pauls, 2023). Hereinafter the Letter will be abbreviated as *Amoris* with page numbers from the book.

“exiled” Bishop of Geneva, whom Pope Benedict XVI called “an apostle, preacher, writer, a man of action and of prayer” (*Amoris*, p. 20), the patron of journalists and communicators, co-founder of the Visitation Sisters, was to ask himself “in every situation in life where the greatest love is to be found” (*Amoris*, p. 11). Pope Francis notes that Pope St. John Paul II called him a “Doctor of Divine Love,” not only for having written “a weighty Treatise on that subject but first and foremost because he was an outstanding witness to that love” (*Amoris*, p. 11). As Pope Francis reflects on “the legacy of Saint Francis de Sales for our time” (*Amoris*, p. 23), he wonders at his “flexibility and his far-sighted vision” in an era of rapid changes (*Amoris*, p. 23). This article is an attempt to understand Pope Francis’ theological vision unraveled in *Totum Amoris Est* as he reflects upon the spiritual legacy of St. Francis de Sales.

Proclamation of the Gospel in Changing Times

Pope Francis describes St. Francis de Sales as “an interpreter of epochal changes and a spiritual guide in an age of renewed thirst for God” (*Amoris*, p. 20). According to Pope Francis, even in early 17th-century Paris, as a fine “interpreter” of his time, St. Francis de Sales, could perceive “clearly that the times were changing” (*Amoris*, p. 23), and this realization that the world was changing made him “respond to those changes with an evangelical sense of the need (*Amoris*, p. 22). Pope Francis observes that St. Francis de Sales might “never have imagined that those changes represented so great an opportunity for the preaching of the Gospel. The Word of God that he had loved from his youth now opened up before him new and unexpected horizons in a rapidly changing world” (*Amoris*, p. 23). “That same task,” says the Pope, “awaits us in our own age of epochal change” (*Amoris*, p. 24). Pope Francis believes that some of the crucial decisions of St. Francis de Sales are “important also today, to live the change with evangelical wisdom” (*Amoris*, p. 24). Therefore, the Pope is asking us, like St. Francis de Sales, to “reinterpret and propose anew to each man and woman the beauty of our relationship with God” (*Amoris*, p. 25).

Love as God’s Grace Tested through Discernment

According to Pope Francis, the ultimate criterion of human life is love, love that is “tested through discernment” (*Amoris*, p. 10), and “attentive listening and acceptance” (*Amoris*, p. 24). The Pope highlights that the great vocation of St. Francis de Sales was that of finding love in every situation of life: “in every situation of life where the greatest love is to be found” (*Amoris*, p. 11). Quoting again St Francis de Sales, the Pope affirms that “it is love that grants perfection to our works. ... it is charity and

love that give value to our works (*Amoris*, p. 10). Pope Francis further says that divine providence draws our hearts to God's love without any imposition but "by invitations, enticements and holy inspirations" (*Amoris*, p. 25).

According to the Pope, although the ultimate criterion of human life is love, this divine grace should not make us passive. Rather, he argues, it should lead us "to realize that God's love radically precedes us, and that his first gift consists precisely in our acceptance of that love. Each person, therefore, is responsible for cooperating with his or her own fulfilment, with spreading his or her wings with confident trust before the gust of God's wind" (*Amoris*, p. 28). Pope Francis believes that man "made by God to fly and unfold all his potential in the call to love, runs the risk of becoming unable to take flight when he falls to the ground and does not consent to reopen his wings to the breeze of the Spirit" (*Amoris*, p. 26). Therefore, he argues, "in the relationship with God, it is always a question of a gratuitous experience, which attests to the depth of the Father's love" (*Amoris*, p. 28).

In a fast-changing world, according to the Pope, St. Francis de Sales considered charity as the only means to heal the world: "The world is becoming so delicate that, in a little while, no one will dare any longer to touch it except with velvet gloves, or tend its wounds except with perfumed bandages; yet what does it matter, if only men and women are healed and finally saved? Charity, our queen, does everything for her children" (*Amoris*, p. 21). This, the Pope remarks "was no pious platitude or an expression of resignation in the face of defeat." Rather, "it was a realization that the world was changing and the mark of a completely evangelical sense of the need to respond to those changes" (*Amoris*, p. 21-22).

St. Francis de Sales, the Pope notes, "had come to realize that desire is at the root of all true spiritual life, but also the cause of its debasement" (*Amoris*, p. 9). For this reason, he "recognized the importance of constantly testing desire through the exercise of discernment" (*Amoris*, p. 10) and found the "ultimate criterion for this assessment is love" (*Amoris*, p. 10), in asking himself "in every situation in life where the greatest love is to be found" (*Amoris*, p. 11). Pope Francis says that "the worship of the human will and its powers, and results in "a self-centered and elitist complacency, bereft of true love" (*Amoris*, p. 8).

Devotion as Concreteness of Love

According to Pope Francis "true and lively devotion presupposes the love of God" (*Amoris*, p. 31), and it is "none other than a genuine, and not generic, love of God" (*Amoris*, p. 31), a manifestation of charity far from being "something abstract"

(*Amoris*, p. 31). Pope Francis teaches that “those who think that devotion is restricted to some quiet and secluded setting are greatly mistaken” (*Amoris*, p. 32). But it “is meant for everyone, in every situation, and each of us can practice it in accordance with our own vocation” (*Amoris*, p. 33). According to Pope Francis, one cannot be devout without the concreteness of love, a “way of life” which “gathers and interprets the little things of every day, food and clothing, work and rest, love and offspring, attention to professional obligations” (*Amoris*, p. 32). Therefore, the Pope says “understood in this way, devotion is far from something abstract” (*Amoris*, p. 32), and “it sheds light on the vocation of each individual” (*Amoris*, p. 32). Therefore, quoting St. Francis, the Pope says that devotion “must be practiced differently by the gentleman, the craftsman, the chamberlain, the prince, the widow, the young woman, the wife. Moreover, the practice of devotion must be adapted to the abilities, affairs and duties of each” (*Amoris*, p. 33). He further explains that true devotion is found in “God’s life dwelling within our hearts” (*Amoris*, p. 31).

Pope Francis explains that “devotion is a sort of spiritual alertness and energy whereby charity acts within us or, we act by means of it, with promptness and affection. For this reason, devotion does not exist alongside charity, but is one of its manifestations, while at the same time leading back to it. Devotion is like a flame with regard to fire: it increases the intensity of charity without altering its quality” (*Amoris*, p. 31). Pope Francis uses the imagery of fire and flame to explain the inherent relationship between devotion and charity: “charity and devotion can be said to differ from one another as fire from a flame. Charity is a spiritual fire that, when fanned into flame, is called devotion. Devotion thus adds nothing to the fire of charity but the flame that makes charity prompt, active and diligent....” (*Amoris*, p. 31). True devotion is “like a flame with respect to fire: it rekindles its intensity, without changing its nature” (*Amoris*, p. 31).

Pope Francis further says, “Francis’ description of false devotion is delightful and ever timely. Everyone can relate to it since he salts it with good humor” (*Amoris*, p. 29). Pope Francis quotes St. Francis de Sales to explain this:

Someone attached to fasting will consider himself devout because he doesn’t eat, even though his heart is filled with bitterness; and while, out of love for sobriety, he will not let a drop of wine, or even water, touch his tongue, he will not scruple to drench it in the blood of his neighbor through gossip and slander. Another will consider himself devout because all day long he mumbles a string of prayers, yet remains heedless of the evil, arrogant and hurtful words that his tongue hurls at his servants and neighbors. Yet another will readily open his purse to give alms to the poor, but cannot wring an ounce

of mercy from his heart in order to forgive his enemies. Another still will pardon his enemies, yet never even think of paying his debts; it will take a lawsuit to make him do so” (*Amoris*, p. 30).

“All these,” Pope Francis said, “of course, are perennial vices and struggles, and they lead the saint to conclude that ‘all these fine people, commonly considered devout, most surely are not’” (*Amoris*, p. 30).

Finding God in the Human Heart and History

According to Pope Francis, the central question of the Saint’s life was, ‘where is God to be found?’ (*Amoris*, p. 11). Pope Francis says that St. Francis de Sales experienced God as “intrinsic to the human heart” (*Amoris*, p. 7), and his life was “completely centered on God” (*Amoris*, p. 6). It is only in the heart and through the heart, Pope Francis argues, that man recognizes God and, at the same time, himself, his own origin and depth, his own fulfillment, in the call to love. Pope Francis stresses that it is essential to start again from the “happy relationship between God and the human being” to reread it and propose it to each person according to his or her own condition, without external impositions or despotic and arbitrary forces, as St. Francis explained in his Treaty. Pope Francis explains this inherent dwelling of God in the human heart in the following way:

An experience of God is intrinsic to the human heart. Far from a mental construct, it is a recognition, filled with awe and gratitude, of God’s self-manifestation. In the heart and through the heart, there comes about a subtle, intense and unifying process in which we come to know God and, at the same time, ourselves, our own origins and depths, and our fulfillment in the call to love (*Amoris*, p. 7).

So, citing the Saint’s *Treatise on the Love of God*, the Pope explains that “at the very thought of God, one immediately feels a certain delightful emotion of the heart, which testifies that God is God of the human heart” (*Amoris*, p. 6-7). “It is in the heart and through the heart” (*Amoris*, p. 7), the Pope writes, “that we come to know God and, at the same time, ourselves, our own origins and depths, and our fulfillment in the call to love” (*Amoris*, p. 7). According to Pope Francis, since the Saint has experienced God as “God of the human heart” (*Amoris*, p. 14), the Saint was “never in danger of attributing theoretical importance to his own personal experience and absolutizing it. Rather, he learned something remarkable, the fruit of grace: the ability to discern, in God, his own lived experience and that of others” (*Amoris*, p. 14).

According to the Pope, finding “God in the human heart” (*Amoris*, p. 7) envisages the essential altruistic love towards fellow brethren. Therefore, Pope Francis observes, “in this light, we can understand why Saint Francis de Sales felt that there was no better place to find God and to help others to find him, than in the hearts of the women and men of his time” (*Amoris*, p. 7-8). Pope Francis further clarifies that “he who presumes to elevate himself towards God, but does not live charity towards his neighbor, deceives himself and others.”

A Renewed Church and Society

Pope Francis’ appeal for the renewal of the Church is well known in his previous writings, and he is exhorting the same in this document too. After the example of Francis de Sales, who “remains a valuable lesson for men and women in our own time” (*Amoris*, p. 33), Pope Francis is challenging the faithful to discern the events of our times with the help of God’s grace and to be a Church that is outward-looking and free of all worldliness:

“We are challenged to be a Church that is outward-looking and free of all worldliness, even as we live in this world, share people’s lives and journey with them in attentive listening and acceptance. That is what Francis de Sales did when he discerned the events of his times with the help of God’s grace. Today he bids us set aside undue concern for ourselves, for our structures and for what society thinks about us, and consider instead the real spiritual needs and expectations of our people” (*Amoris*, p. 24).

So, this is what the Pope envisages for us, for our passing of the era: a non-self-referential Church, free from all worldliness but capable of inhabiting the world, of sharing people’s lives, of walking together, of listening and welcoming. Moreover, Pope Francis is asking the faithful to keep the desire for perfection in every state of life alive while living in the world: “To live in the midst of the secular city while nurturing the interior life, to combine the desire for perfection with every state of life, and to discover an interior peace that does not separate us from the world but teaches us how to live in it and to appreciate it, but also to maintain a proper detachment from it” (*Amoris*, p. 33).

Theology Immersed in Prayer and Community

According to Pope Francis, the Saint’s reflection on the spiritual life is “of outstanding theological importance,” (*Amoris*, p. 14) for it embodies two “essential dimensions of any genuine theology” (*Amoris*, p. 14). The first one is the spiritual

life itself, because “theologians emerge from the crucible of prayer” (*Amoris*, p. 14). It “is in humble and persevering prayer, in openness to the Holy Spirit” that the theologians “attempt to understand and communicate the word of God” (*Amoris*, p. 14). Secondly, it concerns “the ability to think in the Church and with the Church” (*Amoris*, p. 14). The Pope invites the theologians to carry out their work “immersed in the life of the community” (*Amoris*, p. 14).

Faith as an Attitude of the Heart

According to Pope Francis, faith is not a passive surrender to a doctrine without flesh and without history but an attitude of the heart. He says that we discover that faith is not “a passive and emotionless abandonment to a doctrine stripped of the flesh and history” (*Amoris*, p.7) but is “first and foremost an attitude of the heart” (*Amoris*, p.7) that is born from the contemplation of the life of Jesus (*Amoris*, p. 8). Further, he teaches us that “we discover that faith is no blind emotion, but primarily an attitude of the heart, whereby we entrust ourselves to a truth that appeals to our consciousness as a “sweet emotion” and awakens in response, as he was wont to say, an enduring benevolence towards all of creation” (*Amoris*, p. 7).

A New Style of Optimism and Dialogue

In his spiritual direction, Pope Francis explains, St. Francis de Sales speaks in a new way, using a different method, a method “that renounced all harshness and respected completely the dignity and gifts of a devout soul, whatever its frailties” (*Amoris*, p. 19). In this approach, the Pope notes, we can find “the Salesian optimism,” a lasting mark in the history of spirituality that flourished with Saint John Bosco some two centuries later (*Amoris*, p. 19).

After the example of St Francis de Sales, Pope Francis suggests choosing the path of dialogue and charity for a better world. He says that even when confronting Protestants, St Francis de Sales “came to realize increasingly, along with the need for theological discussion, the effectiveness of personal relationships and charity” (*Amoris*, p. 20). He was a “skillful controversialist” (*Amoris*, p. 18) when discussing with Calvinists, but also simultaneously “a man of dialogue,” an inventor of “original pastoral practices,” such as the famous “affiches,” short pamphlets posted everywhere to dialogue with the Calvinists (*Amoris*, p. 16). Further, Pope Francis suggests that there should be a “fruitful synthesis” between “Evangelization and culture for a lasting and promising harvest” (*Amoris*, p. 18).

Discover the Joy of Loving

While summarizing his thoughts on the life of St Francis de Sales Pope Francis remarks that “those who think they are rising to God, yet fail to love their neighbour, are deceiving both themselves and others” (*Amoris*, p. 38). Instead, the Christian life is discovering the joy of loving, and “the source of this love that attracts the heart is the life of Jesus Christ” who gave his life for us (*Amoris*, p. 39-40). According to the Pope, “the ecstasy of life and action is no abstract reality, but shines forth in the charity of Christ that culminates on the cross. That love, far from mortifying our existence, makes it radiate with extraordinary brightness” (*Amoris*, p. 40).

Pope Francis further argues that “life without ecstasy risks being reduced to blind obedience, a Gospel bereft of joy. On the other hand, ecstasy without life easily falls prey to the illusions and deceptions of the Evil one” (*Amoris*, p. 39). Quoting Saint Francis, Pope Francis opines that Christian life is “the ecstasy of work and life” (*Amoris*, p. 35). Further, he says that “Christianity was not to be confused with a facile escapism or self-absorption, much less a dull and dreary obedience” (*Amoris*, p. 35), but “the joyous exuberance of life that transcends the mediocrity of mere conformity” (*Amoris*, p. 36). According to the Pope, “a life ... that rediscovers the wellsprings of joy and avoids the temptation of self-centredness” (*Amoris*, p. 36). Quoting his own Apostolic Exhortation, *Evangelii Gaudium*, Pope Francis explains this point:

The great danger in today’s world, pervaded as it is by consumerism, is the desolation and anguish born of a complacent yet covetous heart, the feverish pursuit of frivolous pleasures, and a blunted conscience. Whenever our interior life becomes caught up in its own interests and concerns, there is no longer room for others, no place for the poor. God’s voice is no longer heard, the quiet joy of his love is no longer felt, and the desire to do good fades. This is a very real danger for believers too. Many fall prey to it, and end up resentful, angry and listless (*Amoris*, p. 37).

Conclusion

As we have seen above, though short in form Pope Francis’ Apostolic Letter *Totum Amoris Est (Everything Pertains to Love)* reveals many of his theological visions for the church and society. While reflecting upon the spiritual legacy of St. Francis de Sales, Pope Francis relates the Saint’s life and mission to the church and society. The Pope identifies the need for proclaiming the Gospel with evangelical wisdom and

asks us to respond to the changes with an evangelical sense of the need. He exhorts us, like St. Francis de Sales, to seek God in every situation of life where the greatest love is to be found. Moreover, he asks us to dwell on the beautiful gift of love through attentive listening, acceptance, and discernment. According to Pope Francis, charity is the only means to heal the world that is broken and divided by various divisive forces. He reflects upon the nature of devotion and asks us to distinguish between true and false devotions. According to him, true and lively devotion is nothing but the love of God and a manifestation of charity.

Pope Francis believes that it is only in the concrete flux of human history and human hearts that man recognizes God. He calls for a non-self-referential Church, free from all worldliness but capable of inhabiting the world, of sharing people's lives, of walking together, of listening and welcoming one another. He dreams of a theology that is rooted in prayer and ecclesial community, and asks theologians to think in the Church and with the Church. According to him, faith is an attitude of the heart rather than a passive surrender to the doctrines of the church. He speaks of a new style of dialogue that renounces all harshness and respects completely the dignity and gifts of every individual and calls for a fruitful synthesis between evangelization and culture for a lasting and promising harvest. Finally, Pope Francis emphasizes that the beauty of the Christian life is discovering the joy of loving after the example of Jesus Christ, our Lord and Saviour.

Thomas Karimundackal teaches Biblical Theology and Biblical Languages at the Faculty of Theology, Jnana Deepa (JD), Pontifical Athenaeum of Philosophy and Theology, Pune, and currently serves as the Head of the Department of Scripture Studies, and the Chairperson of the Doctoral Programme in Theology at JD. He is the editor of *Jnanadeepa: Pune Journal of Religious Studies*, *AUC: Asian Journal of Religious Studies*, *Christ College Pune Research Series (CCPRS)*, and *Wisdom Research Series*. He has authored/edited 12 books and published more than 100 research articles in various national and international journals and periodicals. E-Mail: thomas.karimundackal@jdv.edu.in